

Population Research UK

Our delivery plan 2025 - 2028

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Foreword

The UK's Longitudinal Population Studies (LPS) are a world-leading resource for understanding how lives unfold over time. They provide key evidence for research, policy and practice - yet accessing and working with these complex datasets can be challenging.

Population Research UK (PRUK) was established to help address these challenges by providing coordination, advocacy and strategic leadership across the LPS landscape.

After engaging with the LPS community and listening to needs and priorities, we're now delighted to share our delivery plan setting out the next phase of work between 2025 and 2028.

This plan is the result of consultation across the LPS community and we're especially grateful to the many individuals and organisations who took part in our workshops. Your insights, questions and priorities have shaped our thinking at every step.

What follows is a strategic direction grounded in community input, built on collective ambition and focused on delivering meaningful progress for LPS users and the wider research ecosystem.

We look forward to continuing to work with you as we bring this plan to life and build on the momentum we've created together.

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Context

PRUK is an initiative dedicated to maximising the potential of longitudinal population studies in the UK across social, economic and biomedical research.

Established by the Economic and Social Research Council (ESRC) and the Medical Research Council (MRC), PRUK is supported by a £9 million investment from the UK Research and Innovation Infrastructure Fund to deliver and commission services that enhance population research. We are co-developed by the University of Bristol, University College London, Swansea University, CLOSER and UK Longitudinal Linkage Collaboration (UK LLC).

The UK is home to a uniquely rich and diverse collection of longitudinal studies, including cohorts, panels and biobanks. These resources follow individuals over time, enabling researchers to understand long-term trends in health, behaviour and society.

Despite their value, these studies often remain difficult to access, discover and use. The landscape can appear complex and fragmented, with studies hosted across multiple platforms, using different access routes and metadata standards. This can make it difficult to use longitudinal population studies together, in a coordinated way.

PRUK was created to address these challenges and to serve the full breadth of UK LPS - defined as studies that follow individuals over time using clear sampling methods. Recent reviews and consultations have consistently identified needs and key barriers including:

- **Limited discoverability:** Many LPS datasets are not easy to discover. For example, the [CLOSER Data Audit](#) (2017–2021) covering 64 studies, found that while 95% of shared metadata could be found via three platforms (CLOSER Discovery, UK Biobank and the Gateway to Global Aging Data), this only represented 32% of participants of the 64 studies that made up the audit.
- **Barriers to access:** According to the [Atlas of Longitudinal Datasets](#), most of the 240+ UK studies listed lack a clear access route. Only 22% offer platform-based access; others require contacting study teams directly or provide no visible mechanism for data access at all.
- **Insufficient community support:** Workshops hosted by PRUK and sector consultation, highlight a shared need for:
 - Stronger advocacy to give LPS a unified voice in national infrastructure decisions;
 - A single, searchable catalogue covering the breadth of UK LPS, supported by better metadata and discovery tools;
 - Coordinated training for both researchers and study teams to increase the effective use and stewardship of LPS data.

Our vision

A simplified, interconnected data landscape where LPS data and evidence users experience a seamless journey – from discovering and accessing data to translating those research findings into meaningful societal impact.

Our aim

To achieve more effective interdisciplinary use of longitudinal data and greater impact through empowering users and informing policy.

Our objectives

We will work towards the following objectives to guide our delivery to:

Coordinate and advocate for the LPS community

Enhance discovery capabilities for LPS

Streamline data access processes and mechanisms

Facilitate LPS linked data use

Build capacity and skills for LPS

Our delivery plan

Activity	Objective	Aim	Timeline
1 Community engagement - central PRUK activity	Coordinate and advocate for the LPS community	Bring together a sector-wide LPS community ("PRUK Forum") focused on advocacy, events, Communities of Practice (CoP) and signposting of LPS resources.	42 months
2 Policy coordination secretariat	Coordinate and advocate for the LPS community	Connect policy stakeholders with evidence needs to LPS researchers, provide evidence syntheses and quantify LPS impact.	24 months
3 Searchable register and UK LPS information hub	Enhance discovery capabilities for LPS	Provide a searchable register for all UK LPS – including routes to access, connecting metadata from multiple metadata platforms and enabling search of reusable code.	30 months
4 LPS infrastructure landscape simplification	Enhance discovery capabilities for LPS	Simplify data access by helping studies to share their data in central repositories (UK LLC and UK Data Archive/UK Data Service), including studies nearing the end of active follow-up.	32 months
	Streamline data access processes and mechanisms		
	Facilitate LPS linked data use		
5 Secure data environment training platform	Build capacity and skills for LPS	Create a learning environment populated with synthetic data for researchers to practice and receive training. Commission methodological research to assess representation using linked and whole population data in individual LPS and pooled samples.	18 months
6 UK LPS training resource	Build capacity and skills for LPS	Better understand and signpost the existing UK LPS training offering and commission new training material where gaps exist. Incorporate experiential and innovative approaches to pedagogy.	36 months

Our activities will be delivered through a combination of modes, including the PRUK Coordination Hub, open calls (activities 2, 3 and parts of 5), and partner business cases (activities 5 and 6).

Community engagement - central PRUK activity

Activity	Objective	Aim	Timeline
1	Coordinate and advocate for the LPS community	Bring together a sector-wide LPS community (“PRUK Forum”) focused on advocacy, events, Communities of Practice (CoP) and signposting of LPS resources.	42 months

We will:

- Deliver a programme of advocacy work for the LPS community in the wider data infrastructure ecosystem with government, funders and internationally to serve both national and regional advocacy needs;
- Map the relevant policy, funding and infrastructure developments affecting LPS, collating PRUK Forum feedback on these developments and representing the collective LPS view;
- Develop our website to provide a single landing point for the LPS sector, providing signposting to services, infrastructure, community consultation and promotion of our funded activities and projects;
- Evaluate, promote and develop new Communities of Practice through PRUK’s website and partner networks;
- Organise PRUK-led events for different stakeholders, across multiple locations in the UK;
- Partner with external organisations to list, promote and run joint LPS events;
- Facilitate public and patient engagement in LPS activities through LPS engagement groups and community infrastructures;
- Work with the LPS community to develop a set of ethical standards principles that can be used across LPS research to communicate our values as we engage the public and wider stakeholders.

Policy coordination secretariat

Activity	Objective	Aim	Timeline
2	Coordinate and advocate for the LPS community	Connect policy stakeholders with evidence needs to LPS researchers, provide evidence syntheses and quantify LPS impact.	24 months

We will:

- Map the relevant UK policy stakeholders across central and local government, NHS and other public sector bodies, funders, think tanks, lobbying organisations and charities;
- Engage with key policy stakeholders – through meetings, workshops and other activities - to monitor, understand and document emerging policy evidence needs and share new developments and findings from LPS;
- Engage with LPS study teams and analysts – to share emerging policy evidence needs and scope the utility of LPS data to provide the necessary evidence. Host activities which bring together key policy stakeholders and research analysts together to discuss these emerging policy needs;
- Provide a brokerage service enabling evidence syntheses and linking researchers to policymakers in search of answers to questions where there are evidence gaps.
- Develop methods and metrics for assessment of policy impact from LPS research and scaled up implementation of these metrics.

Searchable register and UK LPS information hub

Activity	Objective	Aim	Timeline
3	Enhance discovery capabilities for LPS	Provide a searchable register for all UK LPS – including routes to access, connecting metadata from multiple metadata platforms and enabling search of reusable code.	30 months

We will:

Organise consultation with users and platform providers to align approaches and to ensure a high-quality user experience in the end design;

Organise consultations with LPS community to agree the study-level metadata content (including available access routes);

Create a searchable register of studies using a minimum standard of metadata that connects to further metadata held in multiple catalogues;

Coordinate and streamline metadata availability to provide integrated search responses and to align LPS profiles across systems;

Embed information about existing LPS access routes into minimum requirement metadata and provide searchable links to LPS-facing code repositories;

Signpost search functionality in existing repositories and guide users to the correct system for their needs;

Develop search functionality to allow aligned re-usable code to be accessed from the LPS register.

LPS infrastructure landscape simplification

Activity	Objective	Aim	Timeline
4	Enhance discovery capabilities for LPS Streamline data access processes and mechanisms Facilitate LPS linked data use	Simplify data access by helping studies to share their data in central repositories (UK LLC and UK Data Archive/UK Data Service), including studies nearing the end of active follow-up.	32 months

We will:

Identify LPS without a hosting solution and invite them into the PRUK scheme;
Develop and launch the concierge service to provide guidance, training and toolkit materials – via the UK LLC governance and ethics “Knowledge Hub” to support onboarding;
Triage studies to consider most appropriate models for hosting and access;
Enable the onboarding of studies into appropriate long-term hosts;
Invite study staff, researchers and stakeholders into CLOSER and PRUK Communities of Practice to learn from wider experience;
Enhance the UK LLC’s governance and ethics “Knowledge Hub” with synthesised evidence of best practice in governance, consent and fair processing and legal basis;
Develop generalisable shared materials (e.g., animations, infographics) to support studies with participant communications as a Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement (PPIE) co-development exercise;
Enable delegated access decision-making for studies with no active PI/representative (e.g. via enhanced UK LLC data application review process).

Secure Data Environment (SDE) training platform

Activity	Objective	Aim	Timeline
5	Build capacity and skills for LPS	Create a learning environment populated with synthetic data for researchers to practice and receive training. Commission methodological research to assess representation using linked and whole population data in individual LPS and pooled samples.	18 months

We will:

Undertake user consultation and needs mapping which will engage stakeholders to define minimum viable requirements for an effective SDE based training platform;

Design and provide training on resource navigation to enhance LPS project planning and data use;

Develop a prototype infrastructure incorporating synthetic data and secure data environment technology;

Generate a Learning Management System using open-source packages allowing asynchronous self-guided training that domain experts can populate efficiently;

Commission the generation of high-fidelity synthetic data that replicates the complex structures and associations found in linked LPS data. Pool LPS data and incorporate synthetic data and training deployment technology into the SDE;

Deploy open science tools within the SDE for learners to share material;

Undertake methodological research to assess the representativeness of LPS data using linked data and the creation of libraries of comparative/standardised and well characterised data and whole population administrative data as a benchmark resource;

Generate and guidance/training outlining the properties of newly available, pooled data to help better understand collective data properties and representation.

UK LPS training resource

Activity	Objective	Aim	Timeline
6	Build capacity and skills for LPS	Better understand and signpost the existing UK LPS training offering and commission new training material where gaps exist. Incorporate experiential and innovative approaches to pedagogy.	36 months

We will:

Conduct a scoping review of existing LPS data science and other relevant training offerings across the UK;

Bring together results from scoping in order to list relevant training opportunities on the CLOSER Learning Hub and also on the PRUK website;

Undertake user consultation and needs mapping for new training content priorities and to identify content and training preferences for different learner groups;

Commission specific training materials from domain experts to address unmet needs;

Incorporate specialist training perspectives to enhance the quality and use of the new learning resources for social and biomedical scientists.

Theory of change

To help achieve our vision, we have developed a theory of change - a structured approach to delivering a programme of activities that outlines the steps needed to reach our desired outcomes.

In our delivery plan, these outcomes represent the changes the LPS community will experience as a result of PRUK's work.

The theory of change sets out a logical flow, defines the areas our work contributes to, illustrates how each element is connected and helps key partners identify their role in the process.

It does this by going from identified need, adding the insights we gain from our consultation and mapping out the activities, outputs and outcomes we will deliver.

Readers can follow the theory of change starting from the identified need for PRUK, then trace how we respond through planned activities, the outputs we expect, and the outcomes we're working toward. This structure makes clear how each part of our work is designed to create impact.

The theory of change provides a high-level overview of the problem we are addressing and the key steps we will take to address it.

As a living document, the theory of change will be reviewed and updated. It also serves as a framework for evaluating PRUK's progress and refining our activities to ensure long-term, forward-looking impact.

Theory of change

Acknowledgements

This document has been developed collaboratively by our team, including the following individuals:

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